

Research Article

Parental Awareness and Health Protocol Practices on HFMD Among Caregivers of Grades 1–3 Pupils in Aklan: A Correlational Study

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<https://doi.org/10.59652/1xy4c21>

Abstract: Hand, Foot, and Mouth Disease (HFMD) continues to pose a public health concern in school-aged children, yet parental understanding and compliance with health measures remain erratic. This study assessed the level of parental awareness and health protocol practices regarding HFMD and examined the relationship between these variables among caregivers of Grade 1 to 3 pupils in a public elementary school in Aklan, Philippines. A quantitative correlational research design was employed. Data were gathered from 166 randomly selected parents and caregivers using a validated, researcher-developed survey composed of 16 true/false items on awareness and 16 Likert-scale items on protocol adherence. Descriptive statistics and Spearman's rho correlation were analyzed using SPSS version 21. Results showed that overall awareness was moderate ($M=10.67$, $SD=2.02$), with lowest scores in etiology (54.97%) and transmission (60.84%) and highest in pathophysiology (80.87%). Health protocol practice was also moderate ($M=2.96$, $SD=0.87$), with variable adherence across promotion, treatment, and rehabilitation behaviors. A weak but statistically significant positive correlation was found between awareness and practice ($r=0.220$, $p=0.004$). These findings indicate that while awareness contributes to better adherence, knowledge alone does not guarantee consistent compliance with preventive measures. Strengthening targeted health education and implementing behavior-focused interventions are recommended to enhance prevention efforts. The study supports the integration of school-based hygiene programs and community-driven health campaigns to reduce HFMD transmission in early childhood settings.

Received: 10 September 2025

Accepted: 20 November 2025

Published: 25 November 2025

Keywords: Hand, Foot and Mouth Disease; Health Knowledge, Attitudes, Practice; Caregivers

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1. Introduction

Hand, Foot, and Mouth Disease (HFMD) is a viral illness predominantly affecting infants and young children, caused by Enteroviruses such as Coxsackievirus A16 and Enterovirus 71 [1]. HFMD is characterized by symptoms including fever, mouth sores, and a rash on the hands, feet, and sometimes the buttocks. Although the majority of HFMD cases are mild and self-limiting, severe cases can lead to complications like meningitis, encephalitis, or even death. In the Philippines, HFMD is a pressing public health concern. Recent data highlights a significant rise in cases, particularly in Aklan, where 136 cases were reported [2]. This alarming increase underscores the urgent need for heightened public awareness and preventive measures.

HFMD poses a serious threat to public health, particularly in children aged one to five years old, who are the most vulnerable population. The Department of Health (DOH) in Western Visayas reported a dramatic increase in HFMD cases, with 3,663 reported as of September 30, 2021, compared to 1,679 during the same period in 2020 [3]. Moreover, in early 2023, the DOH Western Visayas Center for Health Development recorded 2,350 cases from January 1 to February 4, compared to just 132 cases in the same period the previous [4]. Despite advisories on preventive measures such as frequent hand washing and isolation of infected individuals, the rapid rise in cases calls for intensified efforts to educate parents and caregivers on effective health protocols.

Globally and locally, HFMD exhibits notable epidemiological patterns. Studies have shown that HFMD is more prevalent in younger children and often spikes during the rainy season [5]. In the Philippines, urban areas report higher incidences due to population density and limited access to healthcare. The economic burden of the disease is considerable, as caregivers often need to miss work to care for their sick children [6]. These trends are proof that equipping parents with accurate knowledge and effective health practices to mitigate the spread of HFMD is imperative.

Despite public health efforts, as observed by the researcher, several issues hinder the effective prevention and management of HFMD. Not all parents strictly adhere to recommended health protocols, such as wearing face masks, practicing frequent hand washing, and isolating infected individuals. This noncompliance increases the risk of disease transmission. Moreover, there is a gap in knowledge about HFMD among parents and caregivers, leading to delayed diagnosis and treatment. Existing research in other countries assert the critical role of parental awareness in reducing HFMD cases, yet there remains a need for community-level education campaigns to ensure that preventive measures are consistently practiced [7].

While existing studies have examined the epidemiology and impact of HFMD, there is limited research specifically focusing on parental awareness and their adherence to health protocols in the Philippines. A gap exists in understanding how parents perceive HFMD and the extent to which they implement preventive measures in their daily lives. Addressing this gap is imperative to creating tailored interventions that empower parents to protect their children effectively against this looming re-emerging disease.

This study aims to assess the level of parental awareness of HFMD facts, and the extent of their health protocol practices as well as identify existing relationships between these variables. Specifically it aimed to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of parental awareness on HFMD health facts and in terms of (a) Disease Etiology and Incidence, (b) Disease Transmission, (c) Disease Pathophysiology, (d) Treatment and Diagnosis?
2. What is the parental practice level on HFMD health protocol and in terms of (a) Disease Etiology and Incidence, (b) Disease Transmission, (c) Disease Pathophysiology, (d) Treatment and Diagnosis?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the parents' levels of awareness and practice?

By identifying areas where parents may lack knowledge or fail to implement preventive measures, the research sought to identify interventions to mitigate the exacerbation of this disease. The findings of this study will inform public health initiatives aimed at reducing HFMD cases through improved parental education and adherence to health protocols. Additionally, the research will guide healthcare administrators and policymakers in developing strategies to mitigate the societal and economic impacts of HFMD by specifying the areas in which respondents have low awareness and practice levels.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Research Design

This study employed quantitative research, specifically a correlational research design, to evaluate the relationship between parental awareness of Hand, Foot, and Mouth Disease (HFMD) and their adherence to health protocols. Correlational research examines the strength and direction of the relationship between two variables—parental awareness (independent variable) and adherence to health protocols (dependent variable)—without manipulating the respondents [8]. The research design aligns with the study's objectives, which include assessing the levels of parental awareness concerning HFMD facts, such as disease transmission and prevention, and measuring their adherence to health protocols like hygiene practices and isolation measures.

2.2. Population and Sample

The target population included parents and primary caregivers of pupils enrolled in Grades 1 to 3. Using simple random sampling, 166 participants were selected based on the school's enrollment records. Recruitment was conducted with the assistance of school personnel who distributed informed consent forms to eligible participants. Inclusion criteria were: (1) being the parent or primary caregiver of a Grade 1 to 3 student; (2) willingness to participate voluntarily; and (3) ability to understand the Filipino language. Exclusion criteria included: (1) non-parental guardians without daily caregiving roles, and (2) those who failed to complete the questionnaire.

2.3. Data Collection Methods

This study was approved by the Research and Development Office of Aklan State University. Data collection was conducted in April 2024 at a public elementary school located in the municipality of Banga, Aklan, Philippines. A quantitative correlational research design was employed to determine the relationship between parental awareness of Hand, Foot, and Mouth Disease (HFMD) and their practice of health protocols.

A researcher-made questionnaire was used, consisting of three parts: (1) demographic profile, (2) awareness assessment with 16 true/false items covering etiology, pathophysiology, transmission, signs and symptoms, and prevention of HFMD, and (3) health protocol practices measured through 16 Likert-scale statements across promotive, preventive, curative, and rehabilitative dimensions. The instrument underwent face and content validation by public health and science experts and achieved a Cronbach's alpha of 0.87 during pilot testing with 30 respondents, indicating high reliability.

After obtaining consent, questionnaires were distributed during scheduled school meetings or through class advisers and collected within the same week. Anonymity and confidentiality were maintained throughout the process.

2.4. Data Analysis

Collected data were encoded and analyzed using SPSS version 21. Descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, and frequency distribution were computed. To determine the relationship between awareness and health protocol practice, Spearman's rho correlation was used due to the non-parametric nature of the data.

3. Results

The chronology of the results and analyses of the study followed the sequence of the objectives stipulated at the beginning of the study. Thus, this section is divided into the following parts: (1) Awareness of Parents on HFMD Health Facts, (2) HFMD Health Protocol Adherence of Parents, and (3) Relationship between the Parents' levels of HFMD Awareness and Health Protocol Practice.

3.1. Awareness of Parents on HFMD Health Facts

The study findings indicate a generally moderate awareness among parents regarding Hand, Foot, and Mouth Disease (HFMD) health facts, with an overall mean awareness level of 10.67 (SD=2.02), Partially Aware. While parents demonstrate some knowledge about

HFMD, gaps remain in understanding its etiology, transmission, pathophysiology, and treatment. The parental awareness level regarding disease etiology and incidence was found to be 54.97% (SD=0.76 while their awareness of HFMD transmission was slightly higher at 60.84% (SD=0.73), both within the Partially Aware range. The highest awareness level was observed in disease pathophysiology, with a mean percentage of 80.87% (SD=1.07), categorized as Aware. It is followed by HFMD treatment and diagnosis at 70.03% (SD=0.84), also interpreted as Aware. Table 1 provides a summary of the overall awareness levels of primary caregivers.

Table 1. Mean awareness levels of parents on HFMD.

Criterion	Percentage	SD	Description	Interpretation
Disease Etiology and Incidence	54.97%	0.76	Partially Aware	Parents have moderate awareness of HFMD, but their knowledge gaps may lead to inconsistent practices.
Disease Transmission	60.84%	0.73	Partially Aware	Parents have moderate awareness of HFMD, but their knowledge gaps may lead to inconsistent practices.
Disease Pathophysiology	80.87%	1.07	Aware	Parents have good awareness of HFMD but may have minor gaps in understanding or practice.
Treatment and Diagnosis	70.03%	0.84	Aware	Parents have good awareness of HFMD but may have minor gaps in understanding or practice.
Criterion/Indicator	Mean Score	SD	Description	Interpretation
OVERALL AWARENESS	10.67	2.02	Partially Aware	Parents have moderate awareness of HFMD, but their knowledge gaps may lead to inconsistent practices.

Legend:

Criterion Percentage	Score Range	Description	Interpretation
87.50-100	14.00-16.00	Highly Aware	Parents have excellent awareness of HFMD and are likely to follow health protocols effectively.
68.75-87.49	11.00-13.99	Aware	Parents have good awareness of HFMD but may have minor gaps in understanding or practice.
50.00-68-74	8.00-10.99	Partially Aware	Parents have moderate awareness of HFMD, but their knowledge gaps may lead to inconsistent practices.
≤50.00	≤7.99	Unaware	Parents have little to no awareness of HFMD, increasing the risk of non-compliance with health protocols.

3.2. HFMD Health Protocol Adherence of Parents

The practices are categorized into four areas: Health Promotion Practices, Disease Preventive Protocols, Treatment Protocols, and Rehabilitative Protocols. The overall mean health practice level across all categories was rated at 2.96 (SD=0.87), which falls under the Moderate level of practice category. Participants' engagement in health promotion practices related to HFMD was at 3.05 (SD=0.97). In terms of disease preventive protocols, the total mean was 3.01 (SD=0.91) while treatment protocol was at 2.84 (SD=0.96) and rehabilitative protocol at 3.00 (SD=0.99). Table 2 presents the mean scores of the parents' health protocol levels delineating the mean scores in each category.

Table 2. Mean health protocol practice level.

Health Practice on HFMD	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
Health Promotion Practice	3.05	0.97	Moderate level of practice	Parents generally follow health protocols but may have occasional lapses.
Disease Preventive Protocols	3.01	0.91	Moderate level of practice	Parents generally follow health protocols but may have occasional lapses.
Treatment Protocols	2.84	0.96	Moderate level of practice	Parents generally follow health protocols but may have occasional lapses.
Rehabilitative Protocols	3.00	0.99	Moderate level of practice	Parents generally follow health protocols but may have occasional lapses.
OVERALL HEALTH PRACTICE	2.96	0.87	Moderate level of practice	Parents generally follow health protocols but may have occasional lapses.

Legend:

Range	Description	Interpretation
3.51-4.00	High level of practice	Parents strictly follow HFMD health protocols with strong adherence to hygiene and preventive measures.
2.51-3.50	Moderate level of practice	Parents generally follow health protocols but may have occasional lapses.
1.51-2.50	Low level of practice	Parents inconsistently follow health protocols, increasing the risk of disease transmission.
1.00-1.50	Very low level of practice	Parents rarely follow health protocols, posing a high risk of HFMD transmission.

3.2. Relationship Between the Parents' Levels of HFMD Awareness and Health Protocol Practice

The data was subjected to a normality test using the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test, which revealed p-values of 0.000 for the awareness level and 0.001 for the practice level. As a result, a nonparametric test for association was employed. Spearman's rho correlation coefficient was calculated to assess the relationship between the parents' levels of awareness and their level of health protocol practice. Results revealed that there is a significantly weak positive correlation between the parents' levels of HFMD awareness and their level of health protocol practice ($r=0.220, p=0.004$). Table 3 presents the computation.

Table 3. Spearman rho's correlation test for respondents' awareness and practice.

Spearman's rho		Level of Awareness on HFMD	Level of Health Practice on HFMD
Level of Awareness on HFMD	Correlation Coefficient	1	.220**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.004

	N	166	166
	Correlation Coefficient	.220**	1
Level of Health Practice on HFMD	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.004	
	N	166	166

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4. Discussion

The study revealed a generally moderate level of parental awareness regarding Hand, Foot, and Mouth Disease (HFMD). Awareness was lowest in disease etiology and incidence, where many parents lacked knowledge of HFMD’s causative agents, its first clinical description, and the fact that it can also affect older children and adults—findings consistent with several studies [7, 9]. Awareness of transmission was slightly higher, with most parents identifying droplet transmission and handwashing as preventive measures, yet only 15.06% recognized that HFMD can also spread through contact with blister fluid, aligning with the studies of Long et al., and Zhang et al. [10, 11]. The highest awareness was observed in pathophysiology, where most parents recognized both common and uncommon symptoms, consistent with the findings of Mansor & Ahmad [7]. Awareness of treatment and diagnosis was also relatively high, but misconceptions persisted, such as the belief that breaking blisters accelerates healing. These results highlight the need for targeted localized educational interventions, guided by developmental and design theories, to improve not only parental knowledge but also their adoption of preventive practices [12, 13]. Public health efforts—particularly school-based and community-driven programs—can play a critical role in reducing HFMD transmission, as supported by the findings of Zhang et al., Viner et al., and Paul et al. [11, 14, 15].

The study also found that parents exhibited a moderate level of adherence to HFMD health protocols suggesting generally consistent practices with occasional lapses. Health protocol adherence was assessed across four domains: health promotion, disease prevention, treatment, and rehabilitation. In health promotion practices, results indicate that many parents engaged in activities such as proper nutrition and supplementation to boost immunity—practices supported by Zhang et al. and Brega et al., who emphasized the role of parental health literacy in fostering preventive health behaviors [11, 16]. For disease preventive protocols, the mean score reflected a fairly consistent implementation of measures like handwashing, mask-wearing, and physical distancing, though previous studies note that misconceptions and complacency often lead to inconsistency [7, 9]. Treatment protocols scored slightly lower revealing that while parents generally follow appropriate steps such as isolation and consulting health professionals, misinformation persists—particularly the belief that breaking blisters accelerates recovery. Rehabilitative protocols indicated a reasonable adherence to post-recovery hygiene practices, aligning with recommendations from Long et al., and Viner et al., who all highlighted the importance of sustained hygiene to prevent reinfection [10, 14]. Overall, while moderate protocol adherence was observed, the findings underscore the need for integrated school-and-community-based education programs that are contextualized and gender-sensitive [17]. These programs ought to promote accurate health information, dispel treatment misconceptions, and encourage long-term compliance with HFMD prevention and recovery guidelines.

Spearman’s rho correlation analysis revealed a statistically significant but weak positive correlation, suggesting that as parental awareness increases, adherence to HFMD health protocols also improves slightly. This result, while significant, indicates that awareness alone does not strongly predict behavior, aligning with findings from Mansor & Ahmad and Yusop et al., who reported that parental knowledge does not always translate into consistent preventive practices [7, 18]. The weak correlation suggests that other factors—such as access to health

resources, parental motivation, and socio-cultural influences—may substantially affect health behavior. Studies demonstrated that structured, culturally-sensitive, school-based health education interventions significantly enhance compliance with hygiene and isolation protocols, reinforcing the idea that behavior change requires more than knowledge dissemination [11, 12, 13, 17]. Public health programs should therefore go beyond awareness campaigns by incorporating behavioral interventions, such as motivational strategies, parental engagement activities, and community-based reinforcements, to effectively improve compliance with HFMD prevention measures and ensure sustainable health behavior change.

5. Conclusions

While parents demonstrated moderate awareness of HFMD, there were critical gaps in knowledge, particularly in transmission routes and appropriate management. These gaps may contribute to inconsistent adherence to health protocols. The weak correlation between awareness and adherence suggests that additional factors beyond knowledge influence compliance. Motivational factors, cultural beliefs, and perceived severity of HFMD play a role in shaping health-related behaviors. Mere dissemination of information may not be sufficient. Behavioral interventions, community engagement, and structured school-based programs should complement awareness campaigns to enhance parental compliance with health protocols.

Author Contributions: Conceptualization, methodology, writing – review and editing, formal analysis, R.K.N.; Supervision and funding acquisition, D.L.; Project administration, investigation and funding acquisition, J.A., J.G.I.; Investigation, M.E.T. and B.J.F.E. All authors have read and agreed to the final version of the manuscript.

Funding: The study was funded through the Student Development Fund (SDF) of Aklan State University as approved by the Board of Regents during the 89th ASU BOR Regular Meeting held last 24 November 2023 at the Commission on Higher Education, C.P. Garcia Ave., Diliman, Quezon City, Philippines.

Institutional Review Board Statement: The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Institutional Review Board of Aklan State University (28 November 2023).

Informed Consent Statement: Informed consent was obtained from all the respondents of the study.

Acknowledgments: The researchers would like to thank their supportive friends, relatives, family, and God. Gratitude is also extended to the principal, faculty, parents and staff of the research site.

Conflicts of Interest: The researchers declare absence of conflict of interest associated with the contents of this manuscript.

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